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A Study on children's influenced in family purchase decision making with special reference to Coimbatore city

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Abstract

Influence operating on family purchase behavior is the influence of children on the budget allocation and purchases and consumption. There are two type of theoretical approaches that have played a vital role in studying children's influence is affected by a variety of factors, including family variables, namely, social class, family size and family structure, children's characteristics say, gender, birth order and age, parent's characteristics that is education occupation and consumption dependences, Experiences parental potential style and family communication environment.

As soon as children develop the basic skills to communicate they start attempting to influence the family decisions. When compare to younger children Older children have high decision power to take decision in a. As families differ across families and would affect and degree of influence children can exert on purchase decision. In addition, children are also influenced by their families through the socialization process. In the context of consumer behavior the parent- child relationship can be seen as an influence versus yield situation. Children, acting as initiators or influencers seek to influence parents make a particular product/brand decision (to yield). The response of the parent may be modified by enabling condition, or a differing order of expenditure priorities. It has been found that attempts on the part of children to influence purchase decisions of parents tend to decline as they grow up.

Keywords: Communication environment, parent's characteristics, parent-child relationship

Introduction

Economic models of the family treat children either as "goods" in the consumption vector of their parents or as agents with autonomous preferences who are capable of full economic independence. In a developmental trajectory between the infant and the near-adult they know that there are children who have well-defined preferences, who are developing communications and formal reasoning skills, who are capable of productive work and independent action, and who still rely on their parents for guidance and support, but economic theory does not accommodate them easily. During late childhood and early adolescence, children acquire a level of autonomy about their own activities and spending at rates that vary depending on their own traits and abilities, the preferences and resources of their parents, and their environment.

As children being to make choices about how to allocate their time between homework and television, and about how and when to spend their money, they become economic agents engaged in constrained optimization. We know very little about the process by which children acquire this agency; this research provides a first look at child decision-making autonomy from an economic perspective.

The balance that is struck between parental authority and child independence in choices about children's own activities is potentially important for developmental outcomes. Parental restrictions can curtail risky behavior and promote investments in child human capital, but children develop self-confidence by taking independent actions and judgment by experiencing their own mistakes.

Statement of the Problem

Generally both marketers and consumer researchers have ignored children as a consumer segment because, of their title disposable income. Since the 1980's interest has been

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growing contrary to the fractional assumption that parent dominate in family decisions, abundant research has found that, children have substantial relative influence to their parents in family consumption decision. Such an academic finding is actually parallel. The reality in the market place more over particularly in India, considerably less effort has been devoted so far to understanding the role of children in family decisions making.

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the children's choice.
2. To know the role of children's in the family purchasing decision.
3. To study about the extent of children influence in making purchase decision.
4. To identify the nature of production in the children's choice.
5. To study the involvement of parents in satisfying the children's choice.

Scope of the Study

The present study is aimed at filling this gap to certain extent in Indian context by bringing forth the children's choice of influences over their parent, parenting, their personal attitudes and traits and their participation in decision stage and their family communication environment apart from the characteristics, namely, age, education, area and so on. In this regard, a survey has been conducted among two hundred adolescent children in Coimbatore city, with the help of well- designed interview schedule.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no relationship between personal factors of age and children influence to the parents for purchase of goods.
2. There is no relationship between personal factors of gender and children influence to the parents for purchase of goods.
3. There is no relationship between personal factors of class/standard and children influence to the parents for purchase of goods
4. There is no relationship between personal factors of area and children influence to the parents for purchase of goods. influence to the parents for purchase of goods.
5. There is no relationship between personal factors of class/standard and children influence to the parents for purchase of goods
6. There is no relationship between personal factors of area and children influence to the parents for purchase of goods.

Methodology and Research Design

The methodology and design adopted for the study as follows:

Source of Data

The primary objective of the study is to ascertain the children influences in family purchase decision making in Coimbatore. The study is first of its kind and mainly based on primary data was collected through the questionnaires administered to different types of selected sample

respondents. The secondary information were collected from different sources like newspapers, magazines, journals, books, websites and so on., for which the researcher approached various institutions like., Bharathiar University Library, Coimbatore and Research Learning Centre, PSG SCHOOL of management, Coimbatore.

Statistical tools used for Analysis

The primary data have been collected from the potential respondents from different areas and has been properly sorted, classified, edited, tabulated in a proper format and analyzed by appropriate statistical tools. The statistical tests are conducted at 5 per cent level of significance. The following statistical tools are used.

1. Two way table.
2. Chi-square test.
3. Garret ranking technique.

Area of the Study

The study was restricted to children's in Coimbatore city

Limitations of the Study

1. The present study is limited to Coimbatore city only.
2. The sample size was restricted to only two hundred due to time constraints.
3. The findings of the study have been presented based on the information obtained from the respondents of Coimbatore city school children's. Hence it may not be generalized to other areas.
4. The respondents' views and opinions may hold good for the time being and may vary in future.

Sampling Techniques

For the purpose of analysis, the data has been collected from two hundred children's from the selected sampled in schools in Coimbatore city. The samples have been selected on the basis of convenient random sampling techniques. The data has been tabulated and statistically interpreted whenever needed.

Review of Literature

Elizabeth Wolgast's M. (1958) ^[1], "Do Husbands or wives makes the purchase Decision?" investigation revealed that in the American family, economic decisions were most commonly made jointly by husband and wife. There also seemed to be an implicit division of responsibility, growingly more pronounced with increasing age and the length of the marriage. The husband played a major role in planning car purchases and the wife in planning home appliances purchases.

Daniel Starch and staff (1958) ^[2], "Family Decision Making" One of the earliest and the most comprehensive studied examining husband and wife influencing was a commercial study that focused on 12 products grouped into 8 categories which includes both durables and non-durables. Results showed that wives expressed few brand preferences for predominantly masculine non-durable products. They did most of the shopping with an awareness of the brand their husband preferred. The influence of the husbands and wives valued by sub divisions on the durable goods categories.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data Selection of Product Wise Purchasing

S. No	Product	Total Score	Mean Core	Rank
1	Clothes	12598	62.99	I
2	Toys	8480	42.4	VII
3	Snacks	10342	51.71	III
4	Foot wear	10453	52.27	II
5	Bicycle	9483	47.42	IV
6	Books and Magazines	9472	47.36	V
7	Stationeries	8953	44.76	VI

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

Table reveals the reasons for selecting the product. "Clothes" was ranked first by the selected sample respondents with the total score of 12598 and mean score of 62.99. "Foot wear" was ranked second with the total score of 10453 and mean score of 52.27. "Snacks and Bicycle" occupied third and fourth position with the total score of 10342 and 9483 and mean score of 51.71 and 47.42 respectively. "Books and magazines" was ranked fifth with the total score of 9472 and mean score of 47.36. "Stationeries" occupied sixth position with the total score of 8953 and mean score of 44.76. "Toys" occupied last position with the total score of 8480 and mean score of 42.4 respectively. It is evident that most of the respondents gave top preferences for clothes while selecting the product on purchasing.

Relationship between Age and Opinion Regarding Children Overall Influence in Purchase of Goods

Age	SA	A	U	DS	SDA	Total
8 to 11 years	4	10	14	10	10	48
% within age of the respondents	8.3	20.8	29.2	20.8	20.8	100
12 to 15 years	2	6	8	10	20	48
% within age of the respondents	4.3	13	17.4	21.7	42.5	100
16 to 18 years	28	26	20	14	18	106
% within age of the respondents	26.4	24.5	18.9	13.2	17.0	100
Total	48	34	42	42	34	200
%	24	17	21	21	17	100

Square	Value	Df	P.Value
Likelihood raction	27.602	8	.001
Linear by linear	28.024	8	
Association	8.949	1	
No. of Valid cases	200		

Interpretation

It is clear that the P-value is less than 0.05, the between age and opinion regarding children overall influences null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is relationship in purchase of goods.

Relationship between Area and Opinion Regarding Children Overall Influence in Purchase of Goods

Area	SA	A	U	DS	SDA	Total
Urban	12	13	17	22	18	82
%	14.6	15.9	20.7	26.8	22	100
Rural	22	29	25	12	30	118
%	18.6	24.6	21.2	10.2	25.4	100
Total	48	34	42	42	34	200
%	24	17	21	21	17	100

Square	Value	Df	P. Value
Likelihood raction	10.357	4	.035
Linear by linear	10.272	4	.036
Association	1.676	1	.195
No. of Valid cases	200		

Interpretation

It is clear that the P-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is relationship between gender and opinion regarding children overall influences in purchase of goods.

Relationship between Class/Standard and Opinion Regarding Children Overall Influence in Purchase of Goods

Class/Standard	SA	A	U	DS	DSA	Total
4th to 6th	2	10	14	10	10	46
%	4.3	21.7	30.4	21.7	21.7	100
7th to 9th	4	6	8	10	20	48
%	8.3	12.5	16.7	20.	41.7	100
10th to 12th	28	26	20	14	18	106
%	26.4	24.5	18.9	13.2	17.0	100
Total	34	42	42	34	48	200
Percentage	17	21	21	17	24	100

Square	Value	Df	P.Value
Likelihood raction	27.315	8	.001
Linear by linear	28.024	8	
Association	10.772	1	
No. of Valid cases	200		

Interpretation

It shows that the P-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a relationship between class/standard and opinion regarding children's overall influences in purchase of goods.

Findings

Garrett Ranking Analysis

It has been inferred that among the selection of various like clothes, toys, snack etc., the respondents ranked 1st for clothes with average score (62.99).

Two Way Table

When compare to children overall influence to the parents for the purchase of Goods, it is found that 106 respondents are in the age group of 16 to 18 years, 81 respondents are male, 106 respondents are studying in 10th to 12th and 118 respondents are in rural area.

Chi Square Analysis

It has found that there is a significant relationship between age and opinion regarding children overall influence in purchase of goods.

It has found that there is a significant relationship between gender and opinion regarding children overall influences in purchase of goods.

It has found that there is a significant relationship between class/standard and opinion regarding children overall influences in purchase of goods.

It has found that there is a significant relationship between area and opinion regarding children overall influences in purchase of goods.

Suggestions

The following suggestions are recommended for family purchase decision making.

- Children are encouraged to express their idea, which indicates they tend to choose themselves.
- Media, especially television has been pointed out the socialization agents that have a strong influence on children in purchase decision making.
- Parents should teach the children from the earlier age by influencing them with their decision making.
- Children should be encouraged to make their own choice in purchase of goods.
- It is apparent that children as well as adults are enthusiastic participant in the active process of consumption and marketing communications which act as an input to make their decision.

Conclusion

Children constitute an important target market. The amount of influence of children varies with the product category and stage of the decision making process. For some products, they are active initiators, information seekers and buyers, whereas for their product categories, they influence purchase made by the parents.

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Thus products for which children act as purchasing agents should be identified with the help of market research in order to implement or adopt new marketing strategies to promote sale

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